

Policy Learning, Education and Citizen Science Discussion Resource Document

Moderator: Branda Nowell, Professor, College of Humanities and Social Sciences

- [Watch Opening Remarks](#)

Panelists:

- [Bethany Cutts](#), Assistant Professor, College of Natural Resources
 - Twitter: [@BethanyCutts](#)
 - [Watch Opening Remarks](#)
- [Christopher Galik](#), Associate Professor, College of Humanities and Social Sciences
 - [Watch Opening Remarks](#)
- [Louie Rivers III](#), Associate Professor, College of Natural Resources
 - [Watch Opening Remarks](#)
- [Kathryn Stevenson](#), Assistant Professor, College of Natural Resources
 - Twitter: [@drktstevenson](#), [@NCSU_EELab](#)
 - [Watch Opening Remarks](#)

Event Description:

This discussion and the expertise that's represented by our panel of experts asks the audience to reflect on one of the grand challenges associated in the world of climate change. Which is, how is it that we strengthen the linkages between science and action in the climate change arena? How do we learn from the experiences that we're having? How do we get better at disseminating the things that we're learning into policy and practice? How do we get better at engaging citizens in this process?

Translating climate research and scholarship into changes in attitude — and ultimately, public policy and individual behavior — will require an approach to education that inspires participation beyond just the classroom. And citizen science — getting everyday people involved in research by doing things like collecting water samples — could prove to be a critical part of this effort. This panel of experts in participatory knowledge, pedagogy and policy asks the audience to reflect on one of the grand challenges of climate change: Leveraging scientific knowledge to influence widespread action. Discussion focused on ways we learn from collective experience to better disseminate information, shape smarter policy and practice, and engage citizens more effectively in the process.

You can [watch](#) the discussion in its entirety on the NC State Research YouTube channel.

Policy Learning, Education and Citizen Science Discussion Resource Document

Online Resources Shared:

- BRIDGE Project website: <https://bridge.wordpress.ncsu.edu/>
- Cutts: Race and Place - anonymous comments and questions submission form: <https://forms.gle/VCmyjGd9X9ZnoZQc9>
- Race and Place Seminar: Dr. Bethany Cutts: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_B8f51kXD7Y&t=3030s
- Dr. Bethany Cutts Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=lyDRUKMAAAAJ&hl=en>
- Location Matters Lab Facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/LocationMattersLab>
- EE Lab at NC State: go.ncsu.edu/stevenson
- Dr. Kathryn Stevenson Google Scholar: https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aUoIF_AAAAAJ&hl=en
- Center for Family and Community Engagement (CFACE): <https://www.cface.org>

The following questions were answered live during the 2021 University Research Symposium Policy Learning, Education and Citizen Science Discussion. Under each question we provide links you can use to jump directly to the point in the video recording where the question was asked.

Imagine you received a broad call for proposals in the field of climate change and resilience what are some of the big ideas that you'd like to pursue

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

In thinking about how the rules get played and if we can start to create governance mechanisms that exist at this bigger unit of analysis and/or at this point of leverage for doing things like building a better society, **do new options and solutions come up for us that might not have been available before?**

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

How do we find the right analytical level for climate change itself?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

How do we create stronger linkages between science and action in the climate change arena?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)